

Assessment of the Qualitative Characteristics of stored Chicken Table Eggs Coated with Different Edible Oils

Alamuoye Oluwatoyin Folake

Animal Science Department, Faculty of Agricultural Sciences, Ekiti State University

Corresponding Author: oluwatoyin.alamuoye@eksu.edu.ng +2348037439871;

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18677910>

Abstracts

Egg quality deterioration during storage is a significant concern in the poultry industry, affecting consumer preference and market value. This study evaluates the impact of different edible oils (saturated and unsaturated fatty acid) as coating materials on the qualitative characteristics of stored chicken table eggs. A total of 180 Rhode Island Red freshly laid eggs were collected, weighed and randomly allocated to six treatment groups, of 30 eggs each. Each group was replicated in triplicate which comprises of 10 eggs per replicate and each group coated with 50ml oil. Treatment 1 (control) were not coated, treatment 2 (canola oil), treatment 3 (soy oil), treatment 4 (palm oil), treatment 5 (olive oil) and treatment 6 (melted shea butter). All treatment groups were stored in the Laboratory shelf at room temperature (25°C) for a period of 30 days. 10 eggs were randomly selected and assessed for internal and external qualities. 10-member of untrained tastes panelists were employed for the sensorial evaluation of cooked egg samples. The results of study revealed that traits such as egg width, yolk color, albumen weight, shell thickness, egg weight loss, yolk and albumen ratios were not significantly influenced ($p>0.05$) by treatments while egg weight, egg length, yolk weight, yolk height, yolk diameter, albumen width, albumen height, shell thickness, yolk index, albumen index and haugh unit showed significant difference ($p<0.05$) among treatment groups. The study further revealed that coated eggs had appreciable Haugh value an indicator for internal egg qualities, with the highest value observed in Treatment 5 (olive oil) The sensory traits were not significantly affected ($p>0.05$) among treatments. The findings provide insights into the effectiveness of oil coatings in preserving egg freshness, offering a natural and sustainable alternative to conventional storage techniques.

Keywords: Chicken, Table eggs, edible oil, qualitative traits, sensory traits

INTRODUCTION

Eggs, being a crucial source of high-quality nutrition globally, face preservation challenges due to their perishable nature, prompting the exploration of edible oil coatings as a sustainable method to prolong shelf life and maintain quality, particularly in regions with limited cold storage infrastructure (Froiio et al., 2019; Fadda et al., 2022).

The quality of eggs deteriorates immediately after laying due to moisture loss, gas exchange, and microbial contamination, which compromise crucial characteristics like albumen height, yolk index, shell integrity, and Haugh unit, thereby highlighting the

importance of effective preservation strategies, particularly under prolonged storage and ambient conditions (Molnár et al., 2016; Feddern et al., 2017) .

The application of edible oils as a sustainable post-harvest method has shown promise in prolonging the shelf life and quality of eggs by serving as semi-permeable barriers that decrease moisture loss and gas exchange, yet further region-specific research is essential to evaluate the effectiveness of various oils under typical storage conditions, particularly for smallholder farmers and consumers in developing regions (Okiki & Ahmed, 2017).

This study investigates the qualitative properties of chicken table eggs coated with various edible oils during storage by examining factors like weight loss, albumen height, yolk index, and Haugh unit, with the intent of identifying the most effective oil for maintaining egg quality and contributing to better handling practices, enhanced food safety, and diminished post-harvest losses in the egg supply chain.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Site

The study was conducted at the Laboratory of the Department of Animal Science, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State, located in South West Nigeria, under controlled laboratory conditions. The facility was maintained at ambient room temperature 26°C throughout the storage period to simulate typical market storage environments without refrigeration.

Sample Collection and Preparation

A total of 180 freshly laid Rhode Island Red chicken eggs(unfertilized) were obtained from the poultry unit of the Teaching and Research Farm of Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti. Eggs were selected based on uniformity in size, weight (ranging between 55–67g), and the absence of cracks or external defects. The eggs were cleaned with a dry cloth to remove adhering dirt and contaminants before treatment application.

Experimental Design

The experimental design was a completely randomized design (CRD) consisting of six treatment groups:

- Control/ treatment 1: Uncoated eggs
- Treatment 2: Eggs coated with 50 ml Canola oil
- Treatment 3: Eggs coated with 50 ml Soybean oil
- Treatment 4: Eggs coated with 50 ml Palm oil
- Treatment 5: Eggs coated with 50 ml Olive oil
- Treatment 6: Eggs coated with 50 ml melted shea butter oil

180 eggs were randomly allocated to six treatment groups, of 30 eggs each. Each group was replicated in triplicate which comprises of 10 eggs per replicate.

Coating Procedure

Each edible oil was manually applied by immersing the eggs completely for about 30 seconds to ensure full surface coverage, after which excess oil was allowed to drip off before the eggs were placed in storage trays and air-dried for 10 minutes prior to storage.

Storage Conditions

All eggs were stored at room temperature (25–26°C) and relative humidity of approximately 70%. The eggs were stored for a total duration of 30 days.

Parameters Measured

External Quality Parameters

- Egg weight (g): Measured using a digital balance.
- Egg length and width (mm): Measured with a Vernier caliper.
- Shell weight and thickness: Shell thickness was measured at three points (blunt end, equator, and pointed end) using a micrometer screw gauge.

Internal Quality Parameters:

Five eggs each were randomly selected from treatment groups and control, cracked on flat white plate for the determination of internal quality, such as:

- Yolk weight, height, and diameter
- Yolk color: Assessed using the Roche Yolk Color Fan.
- Yolk index: Calculated as Yolk Height / Yolk Diameter.
- Albumen weight, height and width were determined
- Albumen index: Albumen Height / egg width

- Haugh Unit: Calculated using the formula:

$$HU = 100 * \log (H + 7.57 - 1.7W^{0.37})$$

Where H = albumen height (mm), W = egg weight (g)

- Yolk: Albumen Ratio: yolk weight/ albumen weight
- Yolk ratio: yolk weight/ egg weight x 100
- Albumen ratio: Albumen weight/ egg weight x 100
- Egg weight loss: Calculated as the difference between initial and final weight after storage multiplied by 100.

Sensory Evaluation

Sensory properties (aroma, flavor, color, texture, and overall acceptability) were evaluated by a semi-trained panel of 10 members using a 9-point hedonic scale (1 = dislike extremely; 9 = like extremely). The eggs were hard-boiled, coded, and presented in a randomized order under controlled conditions.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) in Minitab statistical software (version 16.1.0.0). Significant differences between means were separated using Tukey's HSD, with significance accepted at $p < 0.05$. Results were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

External and Internal quality determination

Egg Weight and Dimensions

The mean egg weights were significantly different ($p < 0.05$), ranging from 54.5 g in Treatment 4 to 66.3 g in Treatment 2, with Treatment 2 (canola oil) exhibiting the highest weight indicative of superior moisture retention, whereas Treatment 4 (palm oil) displayed the greatest weight loss, reflecting its less effective sealing properties; additionally, egg length significantly varied ($p < 0.05$), with Treatment 3 (soybean oil) recording the largest measurement at 5.84 mm, while egg width did not show significant differences ($p > 0.05$). It suggests that oil coatings exert a more significant influence on longitudinal dimensions compared to lateral dimensions (Narmhikaa, 2022; .

Yolk Characteristics

Yolk weight showed a significant difference ($p < 0.05$), with Treatment 2 (canola oil) producing the highest yolk weight of 19.8 g, indicating a preservation of internal contents attributed to reduced dehydration. Yolk height and diameter were significantly different across treatments ($p < 0.05$), with coated eggs generally retaining better yolk structure than the control. The yolk index, an important freshness indicator, showed significant improvement in coated eggs ($p < 0.05$), particularly in Treatment 6 (31.7 ± 9.88), indicating effective preservation. The yolk color did not vary significantly ($p > 0.05$), implying that oil coatings do not affect pigment retention under the storage conditions used (Faitarone et al., 2016).

Albumen Quality

In the study, significant differences in albumen width ($p < 0.05$) and height ($p < 0.05$) were noted between the treatment and control groups, with the control group exhibiting the widest albumen spread (8.23 mm); typically indicative of aging while coated eggs, especially those treated with olive oil, demonstrated enhanced albumen height (0.73 mm), highlighting the effective role of coatings in preserving egg freshness (Foscolou et al.,

2019; Narmhikaa, 2022), as evidenced by the substantial variance in Haugh unit values, ranging from 59.8 in the control to 83.0% in the olive oil treatment ($p < 0.05$).

Shell and Membrane Parameters

While the weight and thickness of the eggshells did not display significant differences ($p > 0.05$), the weight of the inner membrane varied significantly among treatments ($p < 0.05$), with Treatment 4 (palm oil) exhibiting the greatest membrane weight (0.65 g), likely due to oil absorption, indicating nuanced interactions between oil coatings and the microstructure of the eggshell (Li et al., 2019; Pires et al., 2019; Ratnayake et al., 2021).

Egg Weight Loss

The analysis revealed no significant differences in egg weight loss across treatments ($p < 0.05$), although numerically, coated eggs, particularly those from Treatment 5 at 0.65 g, exhibited less weight loss than the control group at 1.37 g, consistent with previous research indicating that oil coatings create semi-permeable barriers that mitigate water loss and gas exchange (Brasil et al., 2019).

Ratios and Indices

The treatments did not significantly affect the yolk ratio, albumen ratio, and yolk:albumen ratio ($p > 0.05$), although numerically varying values suggested that coated eggs maintained a superior balance, with higher albumen ratios observed in coated eggs and Treatment 6 achieving 59.6%, indicating minimized degradation of albumen mass.

The improvements in Haugh unit, yolk and albumen indices, along with the reduced degradation of coated eggs, support previous findings that edible coatings effectively protect against environmental stressors (Pires et al., 2019; Awwaly et al., 2024; Cortés-Ramírez et al., 2024).

Sensory Evaluation

Aroma

Aroma scores among all treatments were notably consistent, ranging from 5.00 to 5.67, with both the control and Treatments 2 and 5 achieving the highest mean score of 5.67 ± 2.31 , while Treatments 4 and 6 recorded the lowest at 5.00 ± 1.73 , indicating that the oil coatings had a negligible effect on the aroma of stored eggs, likely due to the neutral characteristics of the oils and insufficient storage duration to develop spoilage odors (Brasil et al., 2019).

Flavor

The flavor, a combination of taste and aroma, varied among treatments, with Treatment 5 achieving the highest score (7.00 ± 0.00) due to the preservation of yolk and albumen integrity, while Treatment 2 received the lowest score (5.67 ± 1.53), and both the control and Treatment 4 maintained acceptable flavor scores (6.33 ± 0.58 and 6.33 ± 1.16 , respectively), likely attributed to limited storage duration or favorable conditions.

Color

The color of egg yolk is a significant visual attribute that affects consumer perception, with Treatment 5 achieving the highest color score (7.67 ± 1.16), followed by Treatment 4 (7.00 ± 2.65), indicating that certain edible oil coatings may enhance yolk color during storage, while Treatment 3 also performed commendably (6.00 ± 0.00), and the control along with Treatment 2 exhibited the lowest scores (5.67 ± 2.31 and 5.67 ± 0.58 , respectively), likely due to reduced moisture loss and oxidative changes in certain treatments that preserve pigmentation.

Texture

Treatment 4 achieved the highest texture score (7.67 ± 2.89), indicating a superior consistency preserved by its coating, followed closely by Treatment 5 (7.33 ± 0.58) and the control (7.00 ± 2.65), while Treatments 2 and 6 demonstrated lower scores (6.00 ± 2.00 and 6.00 ± 2.65), suggesting a minor textural degradation likely attributed to less effective coatings in reducing moisture loss and internal pH changes, thus reflecting the sensitivity of egg texture, particularly of the yolk and albumen, to storage conditions, which aligns with the previous studies showing enhanced albumen height and yolk index in select treatments (Awwaly et al., 2024; Sokołowicz et al., 2023).

Overall Acceptability

The overall acceptability, indicating the cumulative effect of all sensory characteristics, revealed that Treatment 5 was the most preferred (7.67 ± 0.58), followed by Treatment 3 (7.33 ± 0.58) and Treatment 2 (7.00 ± 1.00), while the control and Treatments 4 and 6 scored slightly lower (6.33 – 6.67); these high scores for oil-coated treatments suggest that edible coatings effectively enhance or preserve organoleptic quality during storage, with Treatment 5 demonstrating consistent superiority in maintaining freshness and appeal (Feddern et al., 2017).

Table 1.0 Internal and External qualities of uncoated and coated eggs with edible oils

Parameters	control	Treatment2	Treatment 3	Treatment 4	Treatment 5	Treatment 6	p-value
Egg weight (g)	64.9 ± 8.9^{ab}	66.3 ± 8.7^a	64.9 ± 2.54^{ab}	54.5 ± 1.14^b	62.7 ± 2.7^{ab}	61.3 ± 7.7^{ab}	0.033
Egg length (mm)	5.48 ± 0.18^b	5.73 ± 0.10^{ab}	5.84 ± 0.15^a	5.51 ± 0.16^b	5.60 ± 0.25^{ab}	5.58 ± 0.14^{ab}	0.008
Egg width (mm)	4.35 ± 0.15	4.46 ± 0.32	4.42 ± 0.11	4.35 ± 0.22	4.42 ± 0.11	4.48 ± 0.18	0.795
Yolk weight (g)	16.7 ± 1.35^{ab}	19.8 ± 2.36^a	16.5 ± 2.59^{ab}	16.2 ± 0.99^b	19.0 ± 0.61^{ab}	17.7 ± 2.37^{ab}	0.010
Yolk height (mm)	0.60 ± 0.35^b	1.68 ± 0.53^a	1.55 ± 0.15^a	1.45 ± 0.37^a	1.46 ± 0.28^a	1.26 ± 0.3^a	0.000
Yolk diameter (mm)	4.91 ± 0.64^a	4.44 ± 0.42^{ab}	4.02 ± 0.13^b	4.14 ± 0.22^b	4.07 ± 0.28^b	4.01 ± 0.15^b	0.001

Yolk color	8.33±1.37	8.33±1.21	7.67±0.82	6.50±1.52	7.83±1.72	7.00±0.63	0.105
Albumen width (mm)	8.23±1.83 ^a	6.45±0.63 ^b	6.18±0.51 ^b	6.25±0.61 ^b	5.32±0.12 ^b	6.46±1.19 ^b	0.001
Albumen height(mm)	0.42±0.17 ^b	0.68±0.13 ^{ab}	0.67±0.20 ^{ab}	0.58±0.15 ^{ab}	0.73±0.23 ^a	0.52±0.10 ^{ab}	0.029
Albumen weight (g)	31.8±4.56	32.6±4.36	36.5±8.65	28.7±1.01	35.9±8.84	36.6±6.32	0.203
Egg shell wt loss(g)	6.03±0.67	5.46±0.77	5.52±0.97	4.90±0.63	6.02±0.78	5.64±0.58	0.118
shell thickness (mm)	0.04±0.02	0.05±0.02	0.04±0.01	0.03±0.01	0.04±0.01	0.04±0.01	0.186
Inner membrane weight (g)	0.39±0.13 ^b	0.56±0.16 ^{ab}	0.40±0.09 ^{ab}	0.65±0.21 ^a	0.43±0.02 ^{ab}	0.60±0.18 ^{ab}	0.012
Egg weight loss (g)	1.37±1.13	0.82±0.25	0.83±0.25	1.15±0.78	0.65±0.51	1.28±0.65	0.370
Yolk ratio	26.0±3.96	30.0±2.97	25.6±1.76	29.6±1.76	30.3±1.01	29.4±6.12	0.089
Yolk index	0.12±0.07 ^b	0.38±0.10 ^b	0.38±0.04 ^b	0.35±0.09 ^b	0.36±0.06 ^b	31.7±9.88 ^a	0.000
Albumen ratio	49.1±5.41	49.5±5.53	56.0±11.5	52.8±1.24	57.2±13.5	59.6±5.78	0.188
Albumen index	0.10±0.04 ^b	0.15±0.04 ^{ab}	0.15±0.04 ^{ab}	0.13±0.03 ^{ab}	0.17±0.06 ^{ab}	0.12±0.02 ^a	0.022
Yolk: albumen ratio	0.53±0.07	0.62±0.10	0.47±0.13	0.56±0.02	0.55±0.11	0.50±0.10	0.180
Haugh unit	59.8±16.7 ^b	77.8±6.63 ^{ab}	76.0±12.2 ^{ab}	73.4±7.85 ^{ab}	83.04±14.3 ^{ab}	70.6±6.18 ^a	0.030 ^{ab}

Wt- weight; ± mean standard deviation; treatment2- canola; treatment 3-soy oil; treatment4- palm oil; treatment5- olive oil; treatment6- melted shea butter oil

Table 2.0 Sensory properties of coated eggs

Sensory traits	Control/ uncoated	Treatment2	Treatment 3	Treatment 4	Treatment 5	Treatment 6
Aroma	5.67±2.31	5.67±2.31	5.33±2.31	5.00±1.73	5.67±1.53	5.00±1.73
Flavour	6.33±0.58	5.67±1.53	6.00±1.00	6.33±1.16	7.00±0.00	6.00±1.73
Colour	5.67±2.31	5.67±0.58	6.00±0.00	7.00±2.65	7.67±1.16	6.00±0.80
Texture	7.00±2.65	6.00±2.00	6.33±2.08	7.67±2.89	7.33±0.58	6.00±2.65
Over all acceptability	6.33±1.53	7.00±1.00	7.33±0.58	6.67±0.58	7.67±0.58	6.67±2.08

± mean standard deviation; treatment2- canola; treatment 3-soy oil; treatment4- palm oil; treatment5- olive oil; treatment6- melted shea butter oil.

CONCLUSION

This study illustrates that the application of edible oils on chicken table eggs significantly improves various internal and external quality parameters during storage, with Treatment 5 emerging as the most effective in preserving egg weight, albumen and yolk quality, while also positively influencing sensory attributes such as flavor, color, texture, and overall acceptability, thereby supporting the adoption of edible oil coating techniques for post-harvest egg handling, particularly in areas with limited refrigeration where maintaining egg quality is essential for marketability.

RECOMMENDATION

The study demonstrated that the unsaturated edible oil coatings used in Treatments 2, 3, and 5 consistently outperformed those with saturated fatty acids, indicating that the specific omega-3 and omega-6 fatty acids present in these oils are more effective in maintaining egg quality and eating traits. However, treatment 5 showed most superior Haugh value. Therefore, olive oil coated eggs at 50 ml as an edible unsaturated oil could be adopted for use in egg preservation during glut periods and post- harvest handling of fresh eggs.

REFERENCE

- Awwaly, K., Widyastuti, E., Apriliyani, M., Thohari, I., Zuladhar, U., & Rachmawati, A. (2024). The Effect of Casein-Chitosan Edible Coating with Garlic Essential Oil Addition on pH, Haugh Unit and Egg Yolk Index Fresh Chicken Egg on Different Storage. *BIO Web of Conferences*. <https://doi.org/10.1051/bioconf/20248800041>.
- Brasil, R., Cruz, F., Rufino, J., De Oliveira Filho, P., Freitas, B., & Filho, G. (2019). Physical-Chemical and Sensorial Quality of Eggs Coated with Copaiba Oil Biofilm and Stored At Room Temperature for Different Periods. *Brazilian Journal of Poultry Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1806-9061-2018-0930>.
- Cortés-Ramírez, G., Velasco, J., Plascencia, M., Absalón, Á., & Cortés-Espinosa, D. (2024). Development of Edible Coatings Based on Different Biopolymers to Enhance the Internal Shelf-Life Quality of Table Eggs. *Coatings*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/coatings14121525>.
- Fadda, A., Sanna, D., Sakar, E., Gharby, S., Mulas, M., Medda, S., Yeşilçubuk, N., Karaça, A., Gozukirmizi, C., Lucarini, M., Lombardi-Boccia, G., Diaconeasa, Z., & Durazzo, A. (2022). Innovative and Sustainable Technologies to Enhance the Oxidative Stability of Vegetable Oils. *Sustainability*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14020849>.
- Faitarone, A., Garcia, E., Roça, R., Andrade, E., Vercese, F., & Pelicia, K. (2016). Yolk Color and Lipid Oxidation of the Eggs of Commercial White Layers Fed Diets Supplemented with Vegetable Oils. *Brazilian Journal of Poultry Science*, 18, 9-16. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1516-635X1801009-016>.
- Feddern, V., Prá, M., Mores, R., Nicoloso, R., Coldebella, A., & Abreu, P. (2017). Egg quality assessment at different storage conditions, seasons and laying hen strains. *Ciencia E Agrotecnologia*, 41, 322-333. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1413-70542017413002317>.
- Foscolou, A., Critselis, E., Tyrovolas, S., Chrysohoou, C., Sidossis, L., Naumovski, N., Matalas, A., Rallidis, L., Polychronopoulos, E., Ayuso-Mateos, J., Haro, J., & Panagiotakos, D. (2019). The Effect of Exclusive Olive Oil Consumption on Successful Aging: A Combined Analysis of the ATTICA and MEDIS Epidemiological Studies. *Foods*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods8010025>.
- Froio, F., Mosaddik, A., Morshed, M., Paolino, D., Fessi, H., & Elaissari, A. (2019). Edible Polymers for Essential Oils Encapsulation: Application in Food Preservation. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.9b02418>.
- Li, Q., Wang, K., Zheng, J., Sun, C., Ge, C., Yang, N., & Xu, G. (2019). Nanostructural basis for the gloss of chicken egg shells. *Poultry science*. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps/pez329>.
- Molnár, A., Maertens, L., Ampe, B., Buyse, J., Kempen, I., Zoons, J., & Delezie, E. (2016). Changes in egg quality traits during the last phase of production: is there

potential for an extended laying cycle? *British Poultry Science*, 57, 842 - 847. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00071668.2016.1209738>.

Narmhikaa, K. (2022). Influence of edible oil coating on internal quality characteristics and shelf life of chicken eggs stored at room temperature. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2022.13.3.0184>.

Okiki, P., & Ahmed, O. (2017). Preservation of Quality of Table Eggs Using Vegetable Oil and Shea Butter. *International Letters of Natural Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.18052/WWW.SCIPRESS.COM/ILNS.63.27>.

Pires, P., Leuven, A., Franceschi, C., Machado, G., Pires, P., Moraes, P., Kindlein, L., & Andretta, I. (2019). Effects of rice protein coating enriched with essential oils on internal quality and shelf life of eggs during room temperature storage. *Poultry science*. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps/pez546>.

Ratnayake, H., Pitawala, H., & Abeyrathne, E. (2021). Effects of two plant waxes as a coating material on internal attributes of chicken eggs stored under room temperature. *Animal Industry and Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.5187/ait.2021.8.2.65>.

Sokołowicz, Z., Kačániová, M., Dykiel, M., Augustyńska-Prejsnar, A., & Topczewska, J. (2023). Influence of Storage Packaging Type on the Microbiological and Sensory Quality of Free-Range Table Eggs. *Animals : an Open Access Journal from MDPI*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani13121899>.